

In[*]:= $A := \{\{a_1, 0, 0, 0, 0\}, \{0, a_2, 0, 0, 0\}, \{0, 0, a_3, 0, 0\}, \{0, 0, 0, a_4, 0\}, \{0, 0, 0, 0, a_5\}\}$

In[*]:= $Vbasis := \{\{0, 1/a_1, 1/a_1\}, \{0, 1/a_2, -1/a_2\}, \{1/a_3, 0, 1/a_3\}, \{-1/a_4, 1/a_4, 0\}, \{1/a_5, 1/a_5, 0\}\};$

Step 3

scenarios 1

In[*]:= $Ay_1 = A.Vbasis.Inverse[\{\{1, 0, 0, 0, 0\}, \{0, 1, 0, 0, 0\}, \{0, 0, 1, 0, 0\}\}.A.Vbasis].\{c^+_1, c^+_2, c^-_3\}$

Out[*]:= $\{c^+_1, c^+_2, c^-_3, -c^-_3 + c^+_1, c^-_3 + c^+_2\}$

In[*]:= $Ay_2 = A.Vbasis.Inverse[\{\{1, 0, 0, 0, 0\}, \{0, 1, 0, 0, 0\}, \{0, 0, 1, 0, 0\}\}.A.Vbasis].\{c^+_1, c^+_2, c^+_3\}$

Out[*]:= $\{c^+_1, c^+_2, c^+_3, c^+_1 - c^+_3, c^+_2 + c^+_3\}$

scenarios 2

In[*]:= $Ay_0 = A.Vbasis.Inverse[\{\{1, 0, 0, 0, 0\}, \{0, 0, 1, 0, 0\}, \{0, 0, 0, 0, 1\}\}.A.Vbasis].\{c^+_1, c^-_3, c^+_5\}$

Out[*]:= $\{c^+_1, -c^-_3 + c^+_5, c^-_3, -c^-_3 + c^+_1, c^+_5\}$

Step 4

In[*]:= $RTDperp := \{\{1, 0, 1, 0, 1\}, \{0, 0, 1, -1, 1\}, \{1, -1, 1, 0, 0\}\}$

$Z := Simplify[Vbasis.Inverse[RTDperp.Vbasis].RTDperp] (** formula (5.4) **)$

In[*]:= $n1 := Z[[All, 1]]$

In[*]:= $n2 := Z[[All, 2]]$

In[*]:= $n3 := Z[[All, 3]]$

In[*]:= $n4 := Z[[All, 4]]$

In[*]:= $n5 := Z[[All, 5]]$

$cprime := Simplify[-Vbasis.Inverse[RTDperp.Vbasis].\{1, 0, 0\}] * l1 (** formula (5.4) **)$

$S1 = Simplify[$
 $\quad Sqrt[(-cprime + (n1.A.cprime/n1.A.n1) * n1).A.(-cprime + (n1.A.cprime/n1.A.n1) * n1)]$
 $\quad (** formula (6.20) **)$

Out[*]:=
$$\sqrt{\frac{l1^2 a_2 (a_4 a_5 + a_3 (a_4 + a_5))}{a_2 (a_3 + a_4) + a_4 a_5 + a_3 (a_4 + a_5)}}$$

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S2 = Simplify[
  Sqrt[(-cprime + (n2.A.cprime/n2.A.n2) * n2).A.(-cprime + (n2.A.cprime/n2.A.n2) * n2)]
  (** formula (6.20) **)]
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$$\text{Out[*]} = \sqrt{\frac{l1^2 a_1 (a_4 a_5 + a_3 (a_4 + a_5))}{a_4 a_5 + a_1 (a_3 + a_5) + a_3 (a_4 + a_5)}}$$

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S13prep := Transpose[Simplify[
  -cprime + Transpose[{n1, n3}].Inverse[{{n1.A.n1, n1.A.n3}, {n3.A.n1, n3.A.n3}}].
  {{n1.A.cprime}, {n3.A.cprime}}]][[1, All]]
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Simplify[Sqrt[S13prep.A.S13prep]] (** formula (6.20) **)
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$$\text{Out[*]} = \sqrt{\frac{l1^2 a_2 a_5}{a_2 + a_5}}$$

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In[*]:= S35 := Transpose[Simplify[
  -cprime + Transpose[{n3, n5}].Inverse[{{n3.A.n3, n3.A.n5}, {n5.A.n3, n5.A.n5}}].
  {{n3.A.cprime}, {n5.A.cprime}}]][[1, All]]
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Simplify[Sqrt[S35.A.S35]] (** formula (6.20) **)
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$$\text{Out[*]} = \sqrt{\frac{l1^2 a_1 a_4}{a_1 + a_4}}$$

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In[*]:= S15 := Transpose[Simplify[
  -cprime + Transpose[{n1, n5}].Inverse[{{n1.A.n1, n1.A.n5}, {n5.A.n1, n5.A.n5}}].
  {{n1.A.cprime}, {n5.A.cprime}}]][[1, All]]
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Simplify[Sqrt[S15.A.S15]] (** formula (6.20) **)
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$$\text{Out[*]} = \sqrt{\frac{l1^2 a_2 a_3 a_4}{a_3 a_4 + a_2 (a_3 + a_4)}}$$

Step 5

Scenarios 1: $l_0=\{1,2\}$, $l_i=3$

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In[*]:= W1aux := Inverse[{{1, 0, 1}, {0, 0, 1}, {1, -1, 1}}].RTDperp
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In[*]:= W1 := Sqrt[A].Z[[1 ;; 5, 1 ;; 2]].W1aux[[1 ;; 2, 1 ;; 5]].Sqrt[Inverse[A]]
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Simplify[Eigenvalues[Simplify[Transpose[W1].W1], {a1 > 0, a2 > 0, a3 > 0, a4 > 0, a5 > 0}]
  (** formula (6.22) **)]
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$$\text{Out[*]} = \left\{ 0, 0, 0, 1, \frac{(a_1 + a_4) (a_2 + a_5) (a_4 a_5 + a_3 (a_4 + a_5))}{a_4 a_5 (a_3 a_4 + a_2 (a_3 + a_4) + a_3 a_5 + a_4 a_5 + a_1 (a_2 + a_3 + a_5))} \right\}$$